

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Portable, reproducible and scalable bioinformatics workflows using Nextflow and Pawsey Nimbus Cloud	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/VnLX63yXbJU
Nextflow_Nimbus_slides	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record